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Are entrepreneurship policies really benefiting women entrepreneurs?

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Executive summary

Policy is an important component of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, with strong policy frameworks essential for economic growth. Entrepreneurship policy has been shown to be fragmented, disconnected from other policies and ecosystem components, and inherently biased. As a result, women entrepreneurs often fail to benefit from current policy offerings. In this commentary, I draw on a recent OECD-GWEP report to provide some examples of how, for the most part, entrepreneurship policy underserves women entrepreneurs.

Why is entrepreneurship policy important?

Entrepreneurship policy is an important part of the entrepreneurial ecosystem of any country. Indeed, strong policy frameworks are essential for economic growth (Mazaroll, 2014). Policy is typically context based and is both connected to and impacted by other entrepreneurial ecosystem components. This essentially means two things: First, entrepreneurship policy needs to be designed to account for a country's prevailing institutional framework, and second, a change in the policy dimension of the entrepreneurial ecosystem will invariably have a knock-on effect on other ecosystem dimensions such as business supports, culture, human capital, access to finance and access to markets (Isenberg, 2011).

The OECD recently proposed that policy frameworks should be coherent and synergistic across policy areas and be inclusive of underrepresented and marginalized groups of entrepreneurs (OECD, 2022). Furthermore, entrepreneurship policies and their related practices "must be designed to support and advocate for equal and fair participation in entrepreneurial ecosystems" (Treanor & Burkinshaw, 2023, p.3). Unfortunately, entrepreneurship policy has been shown to be fragmented, disconnected from other policies and ecosystem components, and inherently biased (OECD, 2021). This is especially the case for women entrepreneurs who,

evidence suggests, are underserved by current policy offerings (Coleman et al., 2019; Henry et al., 2022; 2023; OECD, 2021; 2023).

Background

In her 2023 commentary for ISBE's *Entrepreneurship Policy and Practice Insights*, Susan Marlow questioned whether entrepreneurship was a positive choice for women given the poor returns, limited welfare benefits and high rates of business exit, which were exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic. She asserts that "bias and discrimination do matter – they need to be revealed and challenged through research and practice" (Marlow, 2023, p.1). The present commentary, while in no way questioning women's fundamental right to engage in entrepreneurship, aims to highlight some of the underlying "bias and discrimination" within entrepreneurship policy by highlighting key policy flaws.

In 2021, the OECD published a report in conjunction with the Global Women's Entrepreneurship Policy Research (GWEP) network that examined entrepreneurship policies through a gender lens (OECD-GWEP, 2021). GWEP research teams were free to choose the specific entrepreneurship policy issue they wished to focus on – typically, the most problematic policy issue in their country at that time. The resulting report critiqued key policy issues across 27 OECD and non-OECD countries under six themes: *Fostering a gender-sensitive entrepreneurship culture (6); Strengthening design and delivery of support (5); Building entrepreneurship skills (3); Facilitating access to financial capital (8); Supporting networks (2) and Building a supportive regulatory environment (3)*. In the commentary, findings from the OECD-GWEP report are drawn on to highlight the various forms of policy flaws and gender biases across the different country policies and to demonstrate how, collectively, these serve to significantly disadvantage women entrepreneurs.

Discussion of key findings

Overarching findings from the OECD-GWEP report can be grouped into five categories, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Findings categories (Source: Author's creation)

A key finding common to many of the countries covered in the report was that there was either **no dedicated women's entrepreneurship policy or only weak references to women entrepreneurs** in the country's mainstream, generic entrepreneurship policy. In those policies where women were mentioned, they were consistently referred to as belonging to a "disadvantaged" or "minority" group, "in deficit" or "lacking" the required entrepreneurial skills and management experience. The conclusion was that such issues could be addressed through more training and mentoring, perpetuating the now rather exhausted "fix the women" argument (Etzkowitz et al., 2001). Furthermore, within many policies there was evidence of a privileging of high-growth, high-tech and export-oriented business sectors – sectors in which women do not typically predominate. These are fundamental flaws within entrepreneurship policy that automatically ascribe to the male model of entrepreneurship, disadvantaging women entrepreneurs from the outset.

Notwithstanding the above, **some countries did have women's entrepreneurship policies**, (articulated either within separate women-dedicated policies or incorporated as dedicated strands within mainstream policies), **but in some cases it was clear that these policies were not working or could be improved significantly**. This was because these policies were often at odds with other ecosystem components such as access to finance or culture or were completely disconnected from other related policies such as those relating to social welfare. Germany was identified as a somewhat unexpected example here. Despite increases in women's entrepreneurship over the years, many of Germany's social welfare policies are still designed around the traditional male bread-winner model, promoting entrepreneurship as a much less desirable career path for women.

Other policy flaws in this category related to policies operating in countries with weak regulatory systems that facilitated discrimination. Pakistan, where levels of women's entrepreneurship are among the lowest in the world, was highlighted as an example, with its weak regulatory systems, limited access to finance and lack of family and social care policies which automatically act against the introduction of any policy designed to encourage women's entrepreneurship.

On a more positive note, GWEP research teams found a small number of instances of **women's entrepreneurship policies that appeared to be working well and could potentially be used as good practice examples for other countries**. Canada, with its dedicated "Women Entrepreneurship Strategy" and, more recently, Ireland, with Enterprise Ireland's "Action Plan for Women in Business", were highlighted as examples of effective government strategies and programmes dedicated to women's entrepreneurship. At the very least, these strategies recognise the need to provide dedicated support for women entrepreneurs, prioritising women's entrepreneurship within the government's broader policy agenda.

The research teams also reported some countries that had **women's entrepreneurship policies but, surprisingly, no actual support programmes linked to these on the ground**, suggesting policy aspirations that had not yet been operationalised. Kenya was highlighted as an

example here, where women constitute almost half of the micro-to-small enterprises and the largest proportion of the informal business sector. However, despite government recognising this in their policies, there was no programme of social protection for women in this sector.

Conversely, the report evidenced some **effective women's entrepreneurship programmes in operation but without formal policies to support them**. Mexico was highlighted as an example here, with some good funding programmes in operation (e.g., Mujeres Moviendo Méjico) but no overarching policy framework to support them. Such programmes had clear sustainability issues and risked being discontinued due to a lack of government commitment and relevant funding.

Across the above thematic areas, the issue of **lack of evaluation** was a common finding highlighted by researchers. Effectiveness reports were often anecdotal, with most policies and their related programmes lacking rigorous evidence-based evaluation frameworks or, surprisingly, failing to include representatives from their target group, i.e., women, in their design, recruitment, management, and assessment processes.

Conclusions

This commentary has attempted to reveal and challenge the “bias and discrimination” in women's entrepreneurship (Marlow, 2023, p1) by highlighting some of the ways in which current entrepreneurship policy disadvantages women entrepreneurs, whether implicitly or explicitly. Findings from 27 countries (OECD-GWEP, 2021) demonstrate that entrepreneurship policy offerings are failing women entrepreneurs globally. Despite some good practices emerging at both the policy and programme level, for the most part, current policy positioning continues to “fly the flag for the male entrepreneur” by implying that women a) are not up to the task of entrepreneurship, b) can only be taken seriously as entrepreneurs if they engage in traditional male-dominated business sectors, and c) risk losing out on other supports by engaging in entrepreneurship due to an imbalanced entrepreneurial ecosystem. Finally, we must remember that policy is context specific. As research has demonstrated, context is particularly important in women's entrepreneurship due to the different challenges women face (Welter, 2019; Henry & Lewis, 2023). Consequently, a “one-size-fits-all” approach is never going to work.

Policy and practice recommendations

Entrepreneurship policy is not a level playing field. However, there are actions that policymakers can take to ensure women entrepreneurs are treated more equally in the policies and programmes they provide. Below are some recommendations policy makers should reflect on:

- **Stop** seeing women entrepreneurs as ‘lacking’ and ‘needing to be fixed
- **Support** those sectors where women predominate (rather than privilege sectors where they do not)
- **Ensure policies and programmes are connected** to the wider E/p ecosystem
- **Embed women's entrepreneurship** into overarching entrepreneurship policy frameworks

- **Highlight and replicate** policies and programmes that work
- **Monitor, evaluate and correct** policies and programmes that do not work
- **Include women** in the design and delivery of entrepreneurship policies and programmes

The above recommendations are intended to level the policy and support 'playing field' for women entrepreneurs. If implemented, these recommendations could not only encourage more women into entrepreneurship but could also provide more targeted support for their entrepreneurial journey, giving them the appropriate time and space to build their business and, consequently, enhance their potential for long term success and survival. Alongside this, researchers in the field of women's entrepreneurship should consider paying more attention to highlighting the impact of their research on policy making (Foss et al., 2019), challenging bias and discrimination and offering concrete policy recommendations. These combined actions could have the power to positively transform the entrepreneurship policy landscape, benefiting policy makers, researchers and ultimately women entrepreneurs.

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